

COMMITTED TO ONE'S OWN FAITH AND DISPOSITIONS FOR DIALOGUE

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Abstract: Christianity has always lived in religious pluralism, from the early Church to the present day. The challenge of Catholicism, then and now, has been to be faithful to one's own faith, yet be open to interreligious dialogue. This paper shows that true openness preserves Christian identity, while fostering mutual enrichment. It critiques superficial approaches that risk weakening faith convictions, but presents various dispositions required for dialogical mission and evangelization.

Keywords: Christian Identity, *Evangelii Nuntiandi*, Faith Commitment, Dangerous Memory, Interreligious Dialogue.

INTRODUCTION

Christianity then and today is faced with the context of religious pluralism. Then, the nascent Christian Church faced the powerful Roman gods, Mystery Religions, influential philosophical movements, etc., yet responded with unwavering faith in Christ and commitment to its vocation to be the Light to the Nations (cf. Isa 49:6, Mt 5:13-16). So also, today in our context the call for the Catholic Church is twofold: (1) remain faithful to Christ and the Gospel and (2) yet enter into dialogue with greater openness and collaborate with other faiths in authentic love. This dual responsibility

becomes all the more crucial to address a fundamental question: What does it mean to be “committed to one’s own faith” while engaging in interreligious collaboration?

In this mission of faithfulness to one’s own faith and evangelizing dialogue, *Evangelii Gaudium* of Pope Francis shows a way forward. It illustrates that “true openness involves remaining steadfast in one’s deepest convictions, clear and joyful in one’s own identity, while at the same time being “open to understanding those of other party” and “knowing that dialogue can enrich each side.”¹ However, in our enthusiasm for interreligious dialogue, some of us, sometimes, enter into simplistic responses. We think, externally and occasionally imitating some of their faith practices, we can manifest our disposition for dialogue with other faiths. In the process, we may mislead others, compromise our faith conviction, or even become superficial in our own faith as well as in other faiths.

In the process of dialogue,

what is not helpful is a diplomatic openness which says “yes” to everything in order to avoid problems, for this would be a way of deceiving others and denying them the good which we have been given to share generously with others. Evangelization and interreligious dialogue, far from being opposed, mutually support and nourish one another.²

Hence, the first element in interreligious dialogue is the conviction and commitment to one’s own faith. Second element is the dispositions towards interreligious dialogue. We shall first explore, what it means to be committed to one’s own faith, for a Christian.

1. COMMITMENT TO ONE’S OWN FAITH

While engaging in dialogue, the partners do not lay aside their respective religious convictions. “The opposite is true:

¹ Francis, Apostolic Exhortation *Evangelii Gaudium* (24 November 2013), no. 251. Cf. John Paul II, Encyclical Letter *Redemptoris Missio* (7 December 1990), 56.

² *Evangelii Gaudium*, no. 251

the sincerity of interreligious dialogue requires that each enters into it with the integrity of his or her own faith.”³ In the Bible, we have an inspiring story of Prophet Elijah and his disciple Elisha from the book of Kings (2 Kings 2:1-12). When the Lord was about to take Elijah to heaven, Elijah told his disciple Elisha, “Stay here; for the Lord has sent me, as far as Bethel.” But Elisha said, “As the Lord lives and as you yourself live, I will not leave you” (2 Kings 2:2). So, they went there. Then, the prophet Elijah said to Elisha, “stay here for the Lord is sending me to Jericho.” But Elisha said, “As the Lord lives and as you yourself live, I will not leave you” and for the third time, Elijah tried to discourage Elisha by saying, “stay here for the Lord is calling me to Jordan.” However, Elisha, who was so convinced about his discipleship, remained faithful in his following his Master. So, he said, “As the Lord lives and as you yourself live, I will not leave you” and they both crossed the river Jordan. On account of his steadfast commitment, Elisha received the double share of the spirit of his Master and went on to do many miracles.

Staying genuinely committed to one’s faith is the way to grow to one’s fullness and this precisely is what every religion actually intends to facilitate in the followers. If Elisha had left Elijah right at the first instance, he would not have got the double portion of the spirit of Elijah. Therefore, first being committed and being rooted in one’s own faith is the beginning of depth and growth and the way to reach one’s full potential. An authentic and mature depth leads to collaboration and dialogue to facilitate a new horizon and a new way of relating with the Divine. Hence, we realize that ‘faith should be firm, but not rigid. Dialogue should be respectful and not compromising.’ This depth comes from one’s own personal encounter with God and God’s revelation.

³ Joint Document of the Pontifical Council for Interreligious Dialogue and Congregation for Evangelization of Peoples, *Dialogue and Proclamation* (Rome: 19 May 1991), no. 48.

1.1 Commitment Rooted in Personal Encounter

Pope Benedict XVI, in his encyclical *Deus Caritas Est*, emphasizes that a deeper Christian faith and identity come from personal encounter with the original source. He writes, “Being Christian is not the result of an ethical choice or a lofty idea, but the encounter with an event, a person, which gives life a new horizon and a decisive direction.”⁴ It is this encounter that re-orient one’s life and determines one’s faith-commitment. It is not only applicable to Christianity, but to all religions in the history. Pope Francis reiterates this in his apostolic letter, *Desiderio Desideravi*: “Christian faith is either an encounter with Him alive, or it does not exist.”⁵ Hence, a believer, first of all, seeks to have a profound experiential encounter of the divine, through sacramental nourishment and doctrinal fidelity. It is with this thirst that St. Augustine writes, “In your sacrament O Christ, I meet you face to face.”⁶

In other words, a spiritual encounter is a mystical way of meeting and knowing Jesus and eventually embodying Christ. St. Paul, who encountered Christ on his way to Damascus undergoes transformation and ever since carries the indelible mark of Christ. Hence, he writes in his letter to the Galatians: “It is no longer I who live, but Christ who lives in me” (Gal 2:20). The encounter with Christ allows both awakening and forming to take place. St. Paul views Christianity as a religion of love beyond all legalistic structures. Similarly, an awakened believer views religion not as an institution for its own sake, but as a reality that seeks to build the Reign of God through collaboration with other faiths and other networks. There will be a greater openness without any insecurity or egoism or superiority. The spiritual encounter transforms us to be liberative in our witnessing to Christ.

⁴ Pope Benedict XVI, *Deus Caritas Est* (25 December 2005), no. 1.

⁵ Pope Francis, *Desiderio Desideravi*, Apostolic Letter (29 June 2022), no.10.

⁶ St. Augustine, *The Apology of Prophet David*, 12.58, *Patrologia Latina*, vol. 14, edited by J. P. Migne, col. 916.

Teilhard de Chardin, a scientist and a theologian, was a man of conviction. In his letter to his cousin, he stresses the aspect of conviction and commitment to one's own faith. He writes, "with God's help, I must live my vision fully, logically and without deviation. There is nothing more infectious than the example of a life governed by conviction and principle. All this, of course, only so long as I am completely faithful to our Lord and his light."⁷ He places loyalty and faithfulness, as a way of life to a person who beholds the vision of God that God desires the salvation of all (cf. 1 Tim 2:4-5). This conviction is infectious and urges the believer to become a staunch disciple, who would engage in the mission of reconciliation and peace building as the ultimate goal of any religion. Then there will not be place for any deviation or compromise. It is applicable to all religions and to every believer having a genuine faith.

1.2 Dangerous Memory Shaping a Common Human Consciousness

The personal encounter is not a passing reality; it leaves a profound memory. Hence, commitment is intrinsically connected to memory. The deeper the memory, the greater will be the commitment for that cause or for that person or for that ideology. Christianity is foundationally a memory religion. Christianity had inherited Judaism's "memorial" character. The German political theologian Johann Baptist Metz emphasizes the centrality of memory in human experience and eventually in spirituality. According to him, memory gives human beings their historical identity: "Identity is formed when memories are aroused."⁸ Memory occupies a central place in shaping our human consciousness

⁷ A. Mannarkulam, "The Eucharist in the Design of Teilhard De Chardin," in *Convergence: A Study on Pierre Teilhard de Chardin and other Eminent Thinkers*, ed. Paul Maroky (Vadavathoor: Oriental Institute of Religious Studies, 1981), 34.

⁸ Johann Baptist Metz, *Faith in History and Society: Toward a Fundamental Practical Theology* (New York: Seabury, 1980), 66.

and collective imagination becoming a foundation for commitment and collaboration.

According to Metz, there are two forms of memory. The first one “does not take the past seriously enough” and in this, “the past becomes a paradise without danger, a refuge from our present disappointments.”⁹ Such memory is superficial; it neither liberates nor transforms but instead fosters exclusivity and introversion.

By contrast, the second kind of memory directly confronts the harsh realities of human suffering and the negative dimension of human existence. Metz describes this as a “dangerous memory,” because it “interrupts” routine existence and “reveals new and dangerous insights for the present.”¹⁰ Such memory purifies religious conviction and becomes the starting point for solidarity, collaboration with people of other faiths, and commitment to justice.

In this context, Metz develops the distinctive notion of “dangerous memory,” which reshapes Christian spirituality. It resists the desire to privatize the memory of Jesus’ death and resurrection and instead situates it within the public and historical struggles of humanity. He further emphasizes the “praxis” of memory, whereby Christians, in solidarity with the victims of history, actively commit themselves to overcoming suffering, oppression, and injustice in the light of God’s promises.¹¹ In this spirit, commitment to one’s own faith, grounded in the dangerous memory, becomes deeper, transformative, and open to collaboration. In this way, dangerous memory connects the paschal mystery to the concrete struggles of the world, making Christian spirituality inherently public and political.

Dangerous memory thus serves as a corrective to any tendency to spiritualize the paschal mystery. It reminds the Church that the resurrection hope is credible only when it

⁹ Ibid., 109.

¹⁰ Ibid., 171.

¹¹ cf. Ibid., 229.

stands in solidarity with the crucified of history. It makes efforts to collaborate with all traditions and faiths to build the Reign of God. It becomes a key hermeneutical tool to deprivatize *kerygma* and make faith and religion a movement towards building a new humanity through interfaith dialogue.

2. DISPOSITIONS FOR DIALOGUE

Interfaith dialogue is not merely a diplomatic or sociological engagement; it is a theological necessity of responding to the Spirit that is working in diverse ways. The Second Vatican Council's *Nostra Aetate* (1965) gave a positive and doctrinal foundation for interreligious engagement. However, there was a slight misunderstanding in perceiving the multidimensional nature of *kerygma* and evangelization. Hence, ten years after the declaration of conciliar document on our relationship with other religions, Pope Paul VI brought out *Evangelii Nuntiandi* (1975) to reiterate the ontological need for proclamation in the light of necessity for interfaith dialogue. *Evangelii Nuntiandi*, thus, presents a dynamic theology of evangelization, which is ingrained with dialogical ethos. It presents evangelization as witnessing and proclamation as relational dialogue. Hence, Stephen Bevans points out that *Evangelii Nuntiandi* "re-conceptualizes evangelization not as territorial conquest but as dialogical transformation."¹² Let us draw inspiration from this document for our second part, to bring out a unified and holistic understanding of the Church's mission that presents evangelization and proclamation in a personal, cultural, witnessing, and relational-dialogical way, ever open and respectful to other faiths.

2.1 Culture as the Primary Locus of Dialogue

One of the crucial dispositions is to recognize the critical crisis of modern evangelization as the rupture between Gospel and Culture. *Evangelii Nuntiandi* (EN) brings out

¹² Stephen B. Bevans and Roger P. Schroeder, *Constants in Context: A Theology of Mission for Today* (Maryknoll, NY: Orbis Books, 2004), 294.

a profound cultural sensitivity and argues that Gospel must purify cultures from within. EN insists that evangelization should not be in a decorative or superficial way, but in a wider and deeper way of making the person as one's starting point and always coming back to the relationships of people among themselves and with God.¹³ In this way, evangelization relates to humans' cultures.

Though the Gospel and the culture are independent and not identical, the realization that the 'Reign of God' is lived by people, who are profoundly linked to a culture, manifests the inherent link between evangelization, culture, and dialogue.¹⁴ Hence, the building up of the Reign of God takes place in and through various elements of the culture of the people. The split between the Gospel and culture needs to disappear and pave way for mutual influence. It leads to possibilities for the evangelization of cultures,¹⁵ so that discriminatory and unjust practices of the cultures can be transformed to become holistic and fruitful.

Religions do not exist outside culture; they are cultural-spiritual universes. The spiritual elements interpenetrate cultural categories and form a new cultural-spiritual universe. Hence, to engage with another religion meaningfully is to engage in its symbolic world with its sacred texts, liturgies, cosmologies, rituals, moral codes, aesthetics, and collective memory. Dialogue is not a mere exchange of doctrines but an inter-cultural encounter. In this light, Avery Dulles claims that EN moves evangelization from the "Juridical frame to the anthropological frame," enabling authentic religious dialogue because "culture becomes the terrain of divine-human-religious mediation."¹⁶ The acknowledgement of cultural richness opens space for recognizing religious values embedded in cultural traditions paving way for a

¹³ Cf. EN 20.

¹⁴ Cf. EN 20.

¹⁵ Cf. EN 20.

¹⁶ Avery Dulles, *Models of the Church* (New York: Image Books, 1978), 92.

new integrated cultural-spiritual universe drenched in love, peace, fraternity, and contentment. One notes that in India faith and culture are inseparably entwined.

2.2 Evangelization as Relational-Witnessing Encounter

Present-day theology increasingly understands evangelization more as a relational and witnessing encounter than a one-directional monologue. It is rooted in the Trinitarian nature of God and God's self-communication. It mirrors a relationship that is doused in divine communion and self-giving love.¹⁷ Divine communion and self-giving love instill in the disciple a spirit of being a witness than a speaker. *Evangelii Nuntiandi* also places witnessing as the foremost way of proclaiming the Gospel. It is about accepting and understanding others, sharing and being in solidarity with the efforts of others in whatever is noble and good. Witnessing is radiating the faith in values that go beyond the current values and hoping in something that is not seen or one would not dare to imagine. This is a wordless witnessing, yet stirs the hearts of people, who ask: why are they like this? Why do they live in this way? Who is inspiring them?¹⁸

Such a silent proclamation of the Gospel is the initial act of evangelization. "Modern [hu]man listens more willingly to witnesses than to teachers... if he[/she] does listen to teachers, it is because they are witnesses" (EN 41). This wordless witnessing involves presence, sharing, and solidarity, which are key to practicing interfaith dialogue. The prioritization of witness subverts the former one-sided communication model. In witnessing, dialogue becomes an existential precondition: one cannot "witness" without entering relational proximity with the religious other. In this model, the pedagogical order of mission moves from instruction to relationship and from argumentation to credibility of life (witness). Dennis Doyle notes that EN

¹⁷ Cf. Karl Rahner, *The Trinity* (New York: Crossroad, 1997), 9-30.

¹⁸ Cf. EN 21.

“perceives evangelization as the radiation of the Gospel by presence before proposition.”¹⁹ It constitutes an implicit paradigm of dialogue that precedes doctrinal exchange and places relational presence as the central element. The witness of life thus becomes a hermeneutical key through which the message of Christ is interpreted and received.²⁰

2.3 Respect for Conscience and Freedom as Precondition

In practicing genuine commitment to one’s own faith, proclamation, constructive dialogue, respect for conscience, and freedom of others are fundamental preconditions. EN strongly rejects coercive mission, emphasizing interior freedom in religious reception. It argues that the Gospel must be proclaimed by witness of life and word, without forcing consciences (EN 79-80). Dialogue presumes liberty, interiority, freedom to practice one’s own faith, moral autonomy of participants, and also accepting their ability to make judgements according to conscience without coercion or fear. Where there is a space for freedom of thought, expression, and belief, there the believers can engage honestly in dialogue with their deepest convictions. Philosophers from Kant to Habermas have argued that dialogue loses its ethical legitimacy, if participants are constrained by external pressures and internalized domination. Following are the elements that would strengthen the process of interreligious dialogue:

i) Respect for freedom enables mutual accountability, as the believers get space to revise their positions based on the newer enlightenment they may receive in dialogue and spiritual conversation.²¹

ii) In interreligious contexts, this respect prevents dialogue from degenerating into manipulation, proselytism,

¹⁹ Dennis M. Doyle, *Communion Ecclesiology* (Maryknoll, NY: Orbis Books, 2000), 178. Cf. EN 41, 76.

²⁰ Cf. Hans Urs von Balthasar, *The Glory of the Lord*, Vol. 1 (San Francisco: Ignatius Press, 1982), 191.

²¹ Cf. Jürgen Habermas, *The Theory of Communicative Action*, Vol 1. (Boston: Beacon Press, 1984), 285-295.

or ideological imposition. It provides respect for the religious and spiritual situation of those being evangelized in their own respective situations.

iii) Respect for conscience also includes recognition of pluralism, acknowledging that differences and disagreements are not a failure but productive elements of dialogical engagement.²²

Here EN converges implicitly with *Dignitatis Humanae* (1965), which asserts that faith cannot be coerced because it is “by its nature a free response to God.”²³ Thus, dialogue is not a strategy but anthropology. It is rooted in the dignity of human conscience and becomes the locus of divine encounter. Thus, the integrity, credibility, and transformative potential of the dialogue process is respected and retained.

2.4 Dialogical Evangelization Animated by Love

“The work of evangelization presupposes in the evangelizer an ever-increasing love for those whom he is evangelizing” (EN 79). It is a love that cares for the other, irrespective of their religious inclinations. What is this love? It is much more than that of a teacher; it is the love of a father; and again, it is the love of a mother (EN 79). It is this love that the Lord expects from every preacher of the Gospel, from every builder of the Church. This love unites people and communities and enlightens us on truth. **Other Signs of love in Dialogical Evangelization are as follows:**

i) Another sign of this love is the care taken not to wound the other person with statements that may need more time and dialogue to understand (EN 79).

ii) Yet another sign of love will be the effort to transmit to Christians not doubts and uncertainties but certainties that are solid because they are anchored in the Word of God.

²² John Rawls, *Political Liberalism* (New York: Columbia University Press, 1984). Cf. Francis, *Evangelii Gaudium*, no. 127.

²³ Second Vatican Council, *Dignitatis Humanae* (7 December 1965), no. 2.

iii) Another sign of this love will be a devotion to the proclamation of Jesus Christ, without reservation or turning back or without hurting others.

2.5 Spiritual Dialogue, through Humility and Grace

While there could be dialogue at many levels, a dialogue between believers is a spiritual dialogue soaked in humility and grace. Interfaith dialogue grows “in the consolation of the Holy Spirit” and by the works of the Spirit. “It is the Holy Spirit who, today just as at the beginning of the Church, acts in every evangelizer who allows himself to be possessed and led by him.”²⁴ This is reiterated in *Redemptoris Missio*, “The Spirit’s presence and activity affect not only individuals but also society and history, peoples, cultures and religions... The Spirit manifests himself in a special way in the Church... but he is also present and active outside the visible boundaries of the Mystical Body.”²⁵ On account of this transcending nature, one realizes that truth cannot be limited and it is received as a gift rather than possessed as achievement.²⁶

The spirit of humility transforms the dialogical space into contemplative experience of more listening than speaking and more discerning God’s revelation than conquest.²⁷ In authentic spiritual dialogue, God precedes the missionary, bestows His grace, works beyond visible ecclesial boundaries, and calls negotiators into humility rather than triumphal certainty. Thus, humility and grace together safeguard the theological depth and transformative power of dialogue.²⁸ In short, spiritual dialogue views evangelization differently as:

²⁴ EN 75.

²⁵ John Paul II, *Redemptoris Missio* (7 December 1990), no. 28.

²⁶ Cf. Augustine of Hippo, *Confessions*, trans. R. S. Pine-Coffin (London: Penguin Classics, 1961), Book X, Chap. 21, 274-280.

²⁷ Cf. Thomas Merton, *New Seeds of Contemplation* (New York: New Directions, 1972), 178.

²⁸ Cf. Bernard Lonergan, *Method in Theology* (New York: Herder & Herder, 1972), 240-244

- i) Rooted in **holiness** (EN 76),
- ii) Conducted in **joyful humility** (EN 79)
- iii) Dependent on the **Holy Spirit as primary agent** (EN 75).

CONCLUSION: IMPLICATIONS FOR THE INDIAN INTERRELIGIOUS CONTEXT

India is characterized by the intersectionality of several religious traditions: Hindu, Muslim, Buddhist, Sikh, Jain, tribal, Christian, secular, and syncretic worlds. *Evangelii Gaudium* insists: “attention must always be paid to the essential bond between dialogue and proclamation, which leads the Church to maintain and intensify her relationship with non-Christians.”²⁹ In this spirit, commitment to one’s faith will lead to a dialogical and integral mission, which will align with India’s religious sensibilities through: (1) witnessing and lived spirituality, (2) religious identity rooted in one’s own culture, (3) mysticism and collaboration as the lingua franca of interfaith dialogue, and (4) collective communitarian experience transcending abstract individualism and ritualism. In this way, our faith commitment itself becomes missional and dialogical in nature. It grows on the fertile soil of presence, humility, mercy, and witnessing encounter rather than winning or conquering. Finally, evangelization is transformed into a dialogical process that invites response rather than demanding assent.

²⁹ Francis, *Evangelii Gaudium*, no. 251. Cf. Indian Bishop’ Conference, *Final Declaration of the XXX Assembly: The Role of the Church for a Better India* (8 March 2013), 8.9.